

Open4UA Action Plan for BERDYANSK STATE PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITY

Action #	Toolkit Recommendation		Pilot Actions	Target for Action
BER01	2.1	The University's research data must be stored in electronic form	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop and disseminate guidelines for storing research data in electronic form. 2. Conduct a training seminar and ensure that researchers transition to electronic data storage using DMPs. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. M06: The guideline is developed and shared for public consultation. 1. M12: The guideline is approved by the Academic Council of the University and published on the University website; all research projects use recommended platforms for research data storage. 2. M06: A training seminar on electronic data storage is conducted. 2. M12: 100% of research project participants use electronic storage with documentation in the DMP format.
BER02	2.2	The University's research data is managed in accordance with the FAIR principles	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conduct a seminar for researchers and PhD students on the FAIR principles and their application in research planning (based on the DIY Data Steward module). 2. Introduce an internal procedure for preliminary FAIR compliance check when submitting DMPs for approval (using a checklist or an adapted F-UJI tool). 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. M06: The seminar program is developed. 1. M12: The seminar is held with the participation of project leaders, researchers, PhD students, and the library. 2. M06: A FAIR compliance checklist is developed; 2 pilot DMPs are evaluated using this checklist. 2. M12: The FAIR compliance check procedure is integrated into the internal DMP approval process.
BER03	2.5	Restrictions on access to the	1. Develop standard protocols for restricted	1. M06: A draft of the restricted access

		University's research data may be established in cases specified by the legislation of Ukraine and/or special agreements on the distribution and use of these data	access to research data, particularly for cases involving: vulnerable groups (e.g. displaced persons, survivors of violence), sensitive personal data (e.g. mental health, trauma, identity), confidential information (e.g. security-sensitive content, unpublished innovations), 2. Develop internal guidelines for assessing risks associated with data disclosure. These will include: classification of data types by access level (open, limited, closed), guidance on anonymization, informed consent, and CARE principles/	protocols is prepared and reviewed by the Research Ethics Committee; piloted in one interdisciplinary project. 1. M12: The protocols are officially adopted and applied in at least 2 ongoing research projects involving sensitive or restricted data. 2. M06: The first draft of the risk assessment guidelines is developed and discussed internally; includes an access classification scheme and practical examples. 2. M12: The final guidelines are published on the university website and integrated into research ethics training and the review process for Data Management Plans (DMPs).
BER04	5.2	When making decisions about the dissemination of research data and other scientific results according to the principles of open science, researchers are required to ensure that the research is not confidential or has not been carried out under contractual terms that make open access impossible	1. Revise the internal procedure for submitting research projects to the Ethics Committee to include a mandatory declaration on the presence or absence of confidentiality or contractual restrictions affecting open access. 2. Develop and publish institutional guidelines on responsible dissemination of scientific results. The guidelines will include: – examples of legitimate restrictions (e.g., embargo periods, metadata-only records, DOI without file), – advice on how to communicate access limitations in DMPs, ethics applications, and publications, – references to international standards (GDPR, CARE principles, etc.).	<input type="checkbox"/> 1. M06: Ethics Committee approves the revised submission form; 3 pilot projects tested the new requirement. <input type="checkbox"/> 1. M12: The updated ethics review procedure is in effect for all new research proposals; ≥10 projects include documented justification of access restrictions. <input type="checkbox"/> 2. M06: Draft of the guideline developed; feedback collected from researchers and ethics advisors. <input type="checkbox"/> 2. M12: Final version of the guideline published on the university website and in the BSPU Open Science community on

				Zenodo; ≥50 researchers have accessed or downloaded it.
BER05	5.3	Providing open access to scientific results and open educational resources that include intellectual property rights owned by other parties is only possible after obtaining permission from the rights holders for such use in accordance with the procedure established by current legislation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prepare a researcher-friendly factsheet on how to obtain permission to reuse third-party content (e.g. images, tables, text excerpts) in open access materials. 2. Introduce an internal checklist to verify the presence of usage rights for all third-party content prior to its publication in open access platforms (institutional repository, Zenodo, OJS) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. M06: A factsheet for researchers on obtaining permission to use third-party content (e.g. images, tables, text excerpts) in open access materials is developed. 1. M12: The factsheet is published on the university website. 2. M06: A draft version of the checklist is developed; piloted with 3 new repository submissions. 2. M12: The checklist is adopted as a permanent requirement for open access submissions.
BER06	5.5	The terms of the Policy do not apply to research data and scientific results that contain information with restricted access	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop an internal guideline for classifying research data by access level (open / restricted / closed), including practical examples from social sciences and natural sciences. 2. Integrate the guideline into institutional data management workflows 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. M06: The guideline is developed and tested in one interdisciplinary research project. 1. M12: The guideline is officially approved; used in active projects involving sensitive data. 2. M06: Draft guideline components included in internal trainings and presented to the Ethics Committee for consultation. 2. M12: The classification guideline is embedded in institutional procedures for project approval and researcher onboarding

BER07	5.7	<p>The University undertakes to provide assistance to researchers on licensing issues, acquisition of intellectual property rights to scientific results and academic texts, and risk assessment of the possibility of premature disclosure of information</p>	<p>1. Conduct a series of consultations and workshops for researchers on copyright, licensing choices (Creative Commons), publishing agreements, and the risks of premature disclosure. 2. Develop an FAQ section on the university website covering common scenarios (e.g., “Can I upload a preprint?”, “How to protect a patent?”, “What should I include in the acknowledgments?”)</p>	<p>1. M06: A workshop and individual consultations are conducted; typical researcher questions are collected. 1. M12: Frequently asked questions are systematized and analyzed. 2. M06: A draft FAQ with the 10 most common questions is prepared and approved by the Research Department. 2. M12: The FAQ is published on the university website and reviewed/updated biannually as needed.</p>
BER08	6.2	<p>The University's open science infrastructure includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● the University's institutional repository – to provide unrestricted access to scientific results and academic texts created by University researchers ● the University's institutional data repository – to provide unrestricted access to research data ● publishing platform for scientific periodicals – for the operation of open access journals that provide free online access to the results of scientific research ● the University's publishing platform – for publishing educational and scientific publications in open access 	<p>1 Conduct an audit and visualization of the existing open science infrastructure elements (as a resource map: platforms, services, responsible units/persons). 2 Develop an integrated landing page “Open Science @ BSPU” — a hub with links to the repository, Zenodo community, journals, guidelines, FAQs, etc.</p>	<p>1. M06: The infrastructure audit is completed; a draft version of the resource map is created. 1. M12: The visual map is available online. 2. M06: A mock-up of the landing page is developed; resources and contact information are compiled; tested with an internal focus group. 2. M12: The hub is available on the university website and includes at least 5 active sections.</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● open scientometric platforms for monitoring and evaluating scientific activity ● server capacity for storing scientific results, research data, open educational resources and tools for securely managing confidential research data ● open source software for scientific research ● open laboratories 		
BER09	7.1	To achieve the goals and objectives defined by these Policy, it is necessary to raise awareness and develop competencies in open science among all participants in the scientific and educational processes of the University	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop and pilot the concept of the “DIY Data Steward” project — an institutional micro-initiative aimed at promoting basic research data management skills through self-learning materials, consultations, and library-based support. 2. Create a dedicated webpage for the “DIY Data Steward” project on the university website, featuring practical tools, templates, brief guides, and curated resources for researchers and support staff. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. M06: Concept of the project developed; core materials (introductory guide, checklist) prepared; small-scale piloting initiated with librarians 1. M12: At least 3 individual or group consultations conducted using DIY materials; feedback collected from participants and used to revise content 2. M06: Draft layout of the project webpage designed; initial set of materials uploaded for review 2. M12: Webpage officially launched under the university domain; includes ≥5 practical resources
BER10	7.2	Examples of work to raise awareness and build competence in open science include the following areas: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● inclusion of open science topics in educational components 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Include a report on the implementation of the University’s Open Science Policy in the agenda of the Academic Council 2. Design and launch a pilot citizen science project at BSPU 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.M06: The report is drafted and presented at a scheduled Academic Council meeting; followed by moderated discussion. 2. M12: Finalized version of the report is published in the BSPU Open Science

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● advanced training of scientific and pedagogical workers ● educational activities (providing recommendations, consultations, conducting seminars, round tables, trainings, etc.) ● public discussions ● special promotions and popularization campaigns (installations, exhibitions, flash mobs, quests, etc.) ● research on open science issues 		<p>community on Zenodo and shared with university stakeholders</p> <p>1.M06: Project description and submission guidelines published on the BSPU website and GitHub repository; the initiative is registered on EU-Citizen.Science and SciStarter.</p> <p>2. M12: The initiative is registered on EU-Citizen.Science and SciStarter. The initiative's pages across platforms have received at least 100 views</p>
BER11	8.1	Achievements in implementing open science practices (in particular, open access to publications and data, contribution to open peer review, development of open educational resources) are taken into account when concluding contracts, promoting and holding a position	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sign and begin implementation of the CoARA Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment at BSPU 2. Launch an internal self-assessment process based on the updated European Charter for Researchers (2023) 	<p>1. M06: The Agreement is signed on the CoARA website; an official statement is published on the BSPU website in Ukrainian and English, explaining its institutional significance.</p> <p>1. M12: A working group or coordinator is designated; a draft roadmap for implementation is developed and shared with academic leadership.</p> <p>2. M06: A Google Form or equivalent tool is created for self-assessment against the 20 Charter principles; initial round of responses collected from academic and administrative staff.</p> <p>2. M12: Results analyzed; used to identify strengths and gaps in current practices; summary report prepared for internal discussion and future action planning.</p>

